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**IMMINENT CONSEQUENCES OF THE
PRIVATIZATION OF STATE-OWNED BANKS: A
CASE STUDY OF IDBI BANK**

BY

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Brief overview of the subject

Banks have always played an essential role in a s economycountry' by maintaining and pumping the flow of money into society. The policies and structures implemented by banks help to mobilise liquidity and to promote asset creation among customers. These roles become even more crucial in developing economies, such as India. Looking at India's population, it is clear that a majority of this population is not financially strong, and therefore the role of banks becomes even more essential. These banks become their security for the future by creating deposits for the welfare of their families, as well as their helping hand in times of need in the form of loans and overdrafts. (Bhattacharjee, 2020).

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However, the Indian economy is marked by a clear divide between public sector or government banks and private banks. Each bank has its own structure and culture of working for the community. While public sector banks are known for their low rates, ease of access and programmes to improve the situation of communities, private banks are primarily target driven, ruthless and highly efficient. This study focuses es on a case study of IDBI Bank (Kumar et al., 2020a).

The Industrial Development Bank of India (IDBI) was initially set up as a direct subsidiary of the Reserve Bank of India. The 's workbank was directly supervised by the Ministry of Finance. However, later, it started operating as an independent bank, though it continued to retain its title. Recently, on 21 January 2019, the Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) purchased 51% of the bank's shares and became its main stakeholder. With this

change in ownership, banks no longer remain under direct government administration, joining the league of private banks. (Anand & Sudarvel, 2020) . Even though LIC is a subsidiary of the Indian government, it should be open to private investment. (Garg, 2019) In addition, the 45% stake in IDBI Bank, which is still held by the government, will be sold to potential private buyers, making the bank a fully private organisation. (Kumar et al., 2020a) .

However, this change of control is not just a change of books; it also transforms the very essence of the bank. Previously, as a government-run enterprise , the bank's main priority was to serve the masses and to provide high-yield savings accounts and insurance policies. Many public banks implement plans and policies to help specific communities or groups of people, such as rural development and cooperative banks. Thus, the fundamental objective of these public banks is not to make a profit, but to help society. (Bhattacharjee, 2020).

However, with this change in ownership, the structure of these banks will change. The objective of the bank will no longer be the development of society, but profit making for stakeholders and investors. (Singh & Das, 2018) The implementation of this objective will lead to a major change in the bank's structure, policies and administrations

To what extent is this change feasible and will result in the good of the bank and society, and what will be its effects, has been at the heart of the debate for a long time in the still existing quarrel between publicisation and privatisation. However, this study focuses on the effect of these changes on bank employees (Kawiana et al., 2018)

In this area, employees have become a major stakeholder in this change. Even a change of hands between two private entities has a significant impact on its employees, let alone a change from a public to a private company (Pattnaik & Panda, 2018).

The bank's employees have been accustomed to a certain type of administration throughout their working lives within the organisation. This administration has been heavily influenced by the organisation's motivations, who it wishes to serve, and how it wishes to serve these customers. (Agnihotri & Gupta, 2019) Most public administrations have limited working hours beyond which employees have no tasks to perform. They are not accustomed to pursuing goals or working for performance-based incentives. The model of government banks has never been profit maximisation, but employees now have to immerse

themselves in a totally different set of ideals to keep their jobs in the organisation (Bhattacharjee, 2020).

Another factor for change is the benefits and guarantees of civil servants. Everyone is aware of the attractiveness of government jobs, which have fixed working hours and secure positions occupied by holders of these jobs until their retirement, compared with the hectic life of business, marked by extensive working hours and very high-pressure jobs.

On the other hand, the change opens up to workers the opportunity to achieve more corporate governance with efficiency rates based on their incentive policies. It will offer better remuneration with greater chances of incentives and promotions based on performance. (Rahman et al., 2020).

Thus, the potential impact of the privatisation of IDBI Bank on its employees can be analysed according to a number of variables. These variables are economic gain, job security, employment, working hours, work culture, employee satisfaction, productivity leadership and team building (Kawiana et al., 2018). Since the complete structure of a company is very different from that of a public company, employees have to undergo major changes to adapt to the new scenario and continue to serve in the organisation. (Agnihotri & Gupta, 2019)

1.2 Problem statement

This change of ownership from government banks to private companies has pushed existing employees into a completely different working life. These employees now have to adapt to the differences in a short space of time with pressure to achieve the company's targets and objectives. This research focuses on changes in working life and the impact of these changes on employees.

1.3 Research objectives

The objective of this research is to examine the potential impact of the privatisation of government banks using IDBI Bank as a case study. However, the main focus of the research is on the impact of privatisation on the bank's employees. To analyse this impact, this research will focus on a number of objectives. These objectives are as follows

- Highlight the advantages of working in both government and corporate structures.
- Examine the differences between the working environment of a public company and that of a private company.
- Analyse the parameters of the changes that employees face as a result of changing jobs.
- Examine the impact of changes on employees.
- Suggestions to facilitate change and help employees get used to the new environment.

1.4 Research questions

This research aims to study the impact of the privatisation of public banks, taking as a case study the IDBI Bank. This thesis focuses on the impact of these changes on employees. To achieve this impact, it is crucial to address a few questions relating to the issue without the answers to which it is not possible to find the answer to the problem. These questions are as follows

1. What are the advantages of working in a public bank?
2. Is it possible to offer these advantages in a private bank?
3. What benefits do private banks offer their employees?
4. How is the working culture in a public bank different from that in a private bank () ?
5. What variables are used to analyse the changes?
6. Is it possible for employees to adapt to these changes in such a short space of time?
7. What recommendations can be implemented to help employees adapt to this privatisation?

1.5 Importance of research

Employees play a vital role in the success of the organisation as a whole. Change profoundly affects the performance and lives of employees, making it difficult for them and the business as a whole to achieve their goals and prosper. This study looks at the changes facing employees and their impact, therefore providing recommendations to help employees cope with such changes and give their best to the business.

Chapter 1 introduces the subject and provides a brief discussion of the subject of the study. It also indicates the aims, objectives and research questions that will be addressed throughout the paper.

In Chapter 2 (), we review the existing literature and identify the gaps in the study that this research aims to fill.

Chapter 3 presents the methodologies used to carry out this research.

In Chapter 4, we calculate the results of the observations

In section 5, we have a wide-ranging discussion of the results and come to a logical conclusion.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

A comprehensive understanding of the Industrial Development Bank of India (IDBI), the meaning of privatisation of government assets, the impact of privatisation of government assets and the privatisation trends of the banking sector in India will enhance the overall understanding of the subject in question. The next chapter of the thesis presents a detailed review of the pre-existing literature on the subject "Potential Effect of Privatisation of Government Banks: Case Study of IDBI Bank". This chapter is divided into four sub-sections, which are followed by a research gap that was established after an exhaustive literature review.

2.1 About IDBI Bank - History (background)

The Industrial Development Bank of India (IDBI) is a private sector bank that was established in 1964. The main function of the bank was to serve as the backbone financial institution for the development of the industrial sector in the post-colonial era. The Industrial Development Bank of India or IDBI Bank has been the subject of many financial studies over the years. The following section of the literature review examines some of the existing literature and evaluates the findings of the study to meet the needs of the proposed thesis.

Rao and Ibrahim(2017) analyse the financial performance of banks in the case of IDBI Bank. The Industrial Development Bank of India lends itself perfectly to this study as it allows the researcher to trace the changes that have resulted from contemporary changes due to the privatisation of the banking and financial sectors. Rao and Ibrahim(2017) focus on the comparison between a newly privatised bank and medium-sized general banks in terms of financial ratio in the Indian banking sector, which consists mainly of public sector banks or PSBs. The financial ratio considered by the authors spans from 2011-12 to 2015-16, i.e. five fiscal years. The results of this study suggest that the financial ratio of IDBI banks is at a regulatory level compared to other financial institutions in the Indian banking sector. The recommendation provided by this study is that banks should exercise practices to improve their overall deposits to provide funds at a lower cost and improve their financial performance.

The Industrial Development Bank of India now falls into the category of 'private sector banks' after becoming a subsidiary of Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) when

the latter acquired more than 51% of the share capital of the former bank. It was originally set up as a scheduled bank during the colonial period under the Reserve Bank of India Act of 1934. This was still the case in 2019. However, , the bank's reputation has been seriously damaged by the increasing number of bad loans granted by IDBI. According to a recent report, in 2021, the loss stood at nearly 4000 crores in the June quarter alone. The primary loan amount stood at over INR 7000 crore. According to the recent financial reforms , the privatisation ation of public sector banks (PSBs) will undergo huge changes. The Indian government has published strategic disinvestment plans for the Industrial Development Bank of India.

A study conducted by Kumar et al. (2020b) raises a very important point regarding the privatisation of banks and its impact on the Indian economy, taking the case of IDBI Bank. The authors define privatisation in the simplest terms, saying that it is a process that involves the sale of public shares and assets to private sector entities. In this process, the overall authority of the government is reduced but there are other benefits, such as the optimisation ation of revenue and capital expenditure, which leads to an increase in the value of the shares of the public entity concerned. The article by Kumar *et al.* (2020b) is a comparative study of the performance of banks before and after privatisation in a developing country such as India. The authors have used several different research methodologies, the main tool of which is the analysis of the financial statements of the IDBI bank. The variables in the same field of study are privatisation ation and the growth of the Indian economy.

Khandelwal(2019) analyses the financial performance of the Industrial Development Bank of India using the efficiency and performance ratio. The essence of this study is based on the post-colonial presence and importance of a financial institution that has provided its services solely to the industrial sector for its immense development and prosperity. IDBI Bank's The main functions of IDBI Bank include a series of responsibilities that the bank assumes. Here are some of these functions .

- Managing funds in the industrial sector and supporting the growth of industries
- Plan and promote the development of industries
- Help fill the gaps and correct the shortcomings in the industrial structuring of by lending upfront funds to support the process.

- Contribute to new floating projects for the vertical growth of the industrial sector in countries such as queen developing India.

In the article by Khandelwal(2019) , the author deals with the efficiency and performance aspects of the Industrial Development Bank of India as the main case study. The authors of the article have evaluated and analysed several efficiency ratios as well as their performance scale. DAS(2020) worked on the non-interest income of the Industrial Development Bank of India (IDBI) and the Industrial Corporation and Investment Corporation of India (ICICI) . The study is comparative at , i.e. examines trends in the Indian banking sector. The last decade has been crucial in this regard, as the banking sector has undergone several changes and developments as it has made its way towards digitisation of the banking sector by leveraging the benefits of technology. The author has studied the non-interest income of these two banks, which are important in India's industrial sector. Non-interest income is generally the charges levied by banks, as defined by the DAS(2020) , which include insufficient funds' fees (ISF), monthly account service charges, inactive fees, short message service fees, deposit and transaction fees, and so on. Needless to say, these services are very different from those of other commercial banks in India, since these two banks cater mainly to the industrial and investment sectors. Thus, this study on the analysis of non-interest income opens the door to further interpretation of the performance of these banks, and the comparative analysis of it is very beneficial for future researchers as well as investors interested in this area of research.

In another comparative study conducted by Dangodara and Joshi(2018) , the authors focused on customer satisfaction. They compared the customer satisfaction ratings of Kotak Mahindra Bank and the Industrial Development Bank of India or IDBI Bank. Kotak Mahindra Bank is quite simply different from the Industrial Development Bank of India () in that it is a bank that provides services primarily to retail customers and the general public, unlike IDBI Bank, which is designed to improve India's industrial sector. Needless to say, the core of the study is based on the fact that the banking sector is highly dependent on customer satisfaction and that it is a "customer-oriented service industry", as defined by the authors. The authors therefore focused on the customer service providers of IDBI Bank and Kotak Mahindra Bank for an in-depth comparative analysis. Mathivannan's study ((2017)) focuses on the non-performing assets of Industrial Development Bank of India (IDBI) and their performance (). The study highlights the importance of the banking sector in a developing

country like India; ; however , with the increasing demand for non-performing assets from banks , they tend to hamper the growth and development of the economy as a whole. Mathivannan(2017) suggests that the negative impact of NPAs affects the liquidity ratio of banks , the competitive advantage, and the overall profitability of banks . In addition, it tends to have a significant impact on the psyche of bankers , as well as on lending and deposits. The study also suggests that banks should monitor their credit mechanisms and periodically inspect all services . This includes regulatory information on annual accounts, share prices, comparative risks, etc. Finally, Mathivannan(2017) recommends that banks should be much more cautious about their assets before they turn into non-performing assets or NPAs.

Musacchio *et al.*(2017) conducted a critical study on the role and development of banks. The study plays an important role by improving the understanding of the procedures of the selected bank, namely Industrial Development Bank of India (IDBI). The authors define development banks as essential tools for holistic economic development . Similarly, they play an important role to correct imperfect market conditions in the event of a crisis. In addition, , development banks are of great help when a particular economy in question is in distress by providing adequate financing to cope with unprecedented economic crises. Banks such as IDBI and ICICI play an important role in promoting and launching projects undertaken by various companies by providing them with financial support. Musacchio *et al.*(2017) underline this in their article from a more general perspective by encompassing the subject in its entirety. For example, the authors highlight how development banks are criticised for their choice of industrialists and their lack of preference for organisations with little influence or budding ations. On the other hand, development banks play an important role as an investment factor in the industrial sector.

Finally, Chahal(2017) studies the application of to the financial analysis and evaluation of the financial position of the Industrial Development Bank of India (IDBI). This paper focuses on recent developments at IDBI and on recent reports relating to IDBI. The study reports on the MoUs that IDBI Bank has recently signed with over 14 state governments and linked them to SHG credits under the State Rural Livelihood Mission (SRLM) in India. The th project launched by the bank is Nishchay, which collaborates with the Boston Consulting Group (BCG). The study analyses in depth the commercial positioning of IDBI and also examines the financial positioning of the ation organisation. Based on a comprehensive understanding of the published literature on the financial analysis

of the Industrial Development Bank of India (IDBI), the authors recommend a series of suggestions, of which the most relevant is the provision of cheaper funds by IDBI Bank to streamline its holistic growth and development.

2.2 Significance of the privatisation of public banks

The process of privatization of government banks is defined as the change of ownership and business format from the hands of the government sector to the hands of the private sector; i.e. , after the process of privatization, the government of the country concerned does not enjoy any kind of authority in the business procedures of the banks (Ramanadham, 2019) . Privatisation is considered to range from improving the efficiency of the bank to improving profitability ratios. Privatisation of India began in 1991 after the 1991 Union Budget, known as the New Economic Policy (Bhattacharjee, 2020) .

It is imperative to examine the idea of privatisation internationally in order to gain a more holistic understanding of the subject . In this respect, the study by Detzer *et al.*(2017) focuses on the issues of privatisation and nationalisation in the German banking system. The privatisation process has had a profound impact on the former state monopolies that existed in the German banking system. Chang(2017) takes a close look at the subject of privatisation and its relationship to economic efficiency. The author focuses much more on the conceptual advantages of privatization and evaluates the claims of the Washington Consensus. Abdeldayem and Dulaimi(2019) tag privatization as a global tool for economic reform. The paper presented by The authors have studied the literature on privatisation in depth in order to gain a better understanding of the concept. The study goes some way to justifying the need for privatisation in less developed countries, as it leads to better governance. The study(2017) by Kozarzewski and Bałtowski, based on Poland, also contributes to concretising the idea of privatisation, as it deals with the effect of change of ownership . It was found that the Polish population was reluctant to respond to privatization, which was launched in 2015.

In another study , Ebrahimi *et al.*(2017) studied the impact of the famous CAMEL model in determining earnings management factors in banks listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange. The authors focus on the CAMEL indices, which influence a bank's earnings management. Needless to say, the most important factor governing investment decisions and

a company's share price is the net profit margin. Ebrahimi *et al.*(2017) provided a detailed justification of why this topic is relevant to the study and introduced the methodological approach of data mining for favourable results tables. They also mention that CAMEL indices are the "most important" factors for determining share and investment prices for banks listed on the Tehran stock market. The sample size of the study is 14 banks, and used the method of regression analysis with the adaptation of panel data. The work is based on six hypotheses in total, including five quasi-hypotheses that point towards the main hypothesis of the study. The results of the research suggest that the CAMEL indices have both positive and negative impacts on the profit management procedures of the banks; however, the asset quality index had little or no effect on the profit management of the banks selected. This study plays an important role in understanding the potential effects of privatisation of government banks with the case study of the Industrial Development Bank of India or IDBI Bank, as this bank alone has a large number of non-performing assets. Earnings management factors and their understanding are crucial to extract the desired results from the proposed thesis.

Mercille and Murphy(2017) explicitly explore the meaning of privatisation and propose a political-economic framework for a comprehensive understanding of privatisation. The examples examined by Mercille and Murphy(2017) come from contemporary Europe, and the concepts discussed in this article are privatisation in relation to liberalisation and commercialisation. The authors discuss the schematic framework of privatisation as a whole. The main objective of this paper is to provide more literature on the related issues of privatisation, as most of the literature in this area consists of case studies. Thus, a framework for understanding the concept of privatisation is extremely useful for studying the potential effects of the privatisation of state-owned banks.

2.3 Trends in the privatisation of state-owned banks in India

The trend towards privatisation of government assets in India has become the latest topic of discussion in academic circles as well as in general discussions globally. In this process, recent developments in the banking sector in India have been privatisation of government banks. In this process, private companies are acquiring government assets in order to give a larger image of the economy. The privatisation of banks has both positive impacts and negative impacts on the financial sector. In a recent report published by the Times of India (Kembai Srinivasa Rao, 2021), the Indian Union Budget for 2021-

2022 has suggested launching privatisation of government banks or public sector banks (PSBs). Initially, the privatised banks were Indian Overseas Bank (IOB), Bank of India (BOI), Central Bank of India (CBI), and Bank of Maharashtra (BOM). All these banks were shortlisted by NITI Aayog.

Numerous studies have been carried out on the reasons why the privatisation process of banks in India is necessary. In the speech, the reasons were enumerated, ranging from the need to expand the banks and strengthen the country's banking and financial sector to the desire to be part of a larger project to contribute to the growth and development of the Indian economy. The privatisation of government-run banks has led to positive changes in the financial position of banks, as well as improvements in the services they provide. Many argue that privatisation is a profit-driven project that seriously undermines consumers' right to information (RTI). In addition, some argue that private sector banks tend to target the upper end of society with high incomes in metropolitan cities, while the poorer and rural areas are excluded from the benefits of privatisation of government banks. On the other hand, the nationalisation of banks was a step towards rectifying the bank failures, strengthening the stability of the banking sector in India and improving the long-term accountability of banks. All these factors determine whether the profitability of banks has improved.

Bapat(2018) has been working on issues related to profitability and its drivers. This study focuses on the specific factors that determine profitability in the Indian banking sector. The authors examine financial and other prior data from the year 2006-07 to 2012-13 for both private sector banks and public sector banks. The study includes dependent and independent variables, which are as follows: The dependent variables are return on equity and average assets; Independent variable - factors determining the profitability of the banking sector in India. The factors that determine the growth and profitability of the banking sector range from factors directly related to the banking industry to economic factors. The results of the study suggest that the non-performing loans granted by banks are those that match the losses of banks. In addition, the cost of income is indirectly proportional to the improvement in the bank's profitability. As Bapat acknowledges,(2018) measures to diversify the banking sector play only a limited role, if any, in increasing the profitability of banks. Thus, the privatisation of banks is another reason for the implementation of regulatory measures in banks.

In this respect, Patel(2018) has conducted a study on the subject of bank mergers from an Indian perspective. The study is comparative in nature, making a clear distinction between the pre-merger period and the post-merger period in order to detect the impact of the merger on the long-term profit ratio of Indian banks. The data collected by the author covers a ten-year period from 2003-2004 to 2013-2014. The financial performance considered by the author is studied in relation to the associated variables . The results suggest that mergers have negative consequences on bank equity, net profit, investment and return on assets. On the other hand, the positive consequences of mergers are on employees and activity per employee. The authors consider the examples of the Bank of Baroda and the Oriental Bank of Commerce, whose returns on advances and investments are strongly affected in the period following the merger. On the other hand, banks such as the State Bank of India (SBI) and the Industrial Development Bank of India (IDBI) have a positive impact on activity per employee and profit per employee compared with the sector average in India.

The study by Tadas(2021) is in the same field, but it deals only with the benefits of mergers in banks in the Indian banking sector. The main objective of this study is quite similar to Patel's comparative study(2018) on mergers. Tadas(2021) focuses on the study of pre-merger conditions in the Indian banking system and analyses the impact of mergers or privatisation in the Indian banking sector. Jegadeeshwaran and Basuvaraj(2019) have analysed the state of credit risk growth of selected public sector banks in India. The author highlights non-performing assets as the biggest challenge for the Indian banking system. This study focuses on non-performing assets of banks such as Punjab National Bank, Industrial Development Bank of India (IDBI), Bank of Baroda (BOB), Union Bank of India (UBI), Central Bank of India (CBI), Bank of India, Indian Overseas Bank (IOB), and Oriental Bank of Commerce. The data collected for the study spans ten years, from 2007-08 to 2017-18. The methodology used for the study is ratio analysis and descriptive statistics, and the conclusion of the study is that there is a huge amount of non-performing assets in Industrial Development Bank of India (IDBI) and it is in financial distress.

In studying the trend towards privatisation in India, it is important to understand the depths of India's private sector banks and how they improve business, efficiency, productivity and soundness, as studied by Uppal(2020) . The main objective of this study was to analyse these factors in relation to the objective ranking method. The data taken into

account are those for 1999-2000 and 2000-01. The study sample is eight new private sector banks for the study of the four factors mentioned above, as follows:

- IDBI Bank
- GT Bank
- HDFC Bank
- ICICI Bank
- Bank of Indusland
- Centurion Bank
- BOP Ltd.
- UTI Bank

The results of this study, after analysis, indicate the ranking of these new private sector banks (NPSBs) in terms of succession, business performance, soundness and efficiency. The author found that in terms of efficiency, Industrial Development Bank of India (IDBI) occupies the third position, based on the data collected on it as a new privatised bank ed. Similarly, labo r the productivity of the Industrial Development Bank of India is equally high.

On the basis of a study conducted by Marvadi(2018) , the author studies the determinants which affect banking efficiency using the Camel model for selected Indian banks. Using this model, the author evaluates the following five parameters in the banking sector: capital adequacy, asset quality, management efficiency, earnings quality and liquidity capacity. The sample size for banks is four public sector banks and four private sector banks, and the period considered is ten years, from 2005 to 2006 to 2014- 2015. The results suggest that the Industrial Development Bank of India (IDBI) has achieved its latest position in determining banking efficiency using the Camel analysis model. The author also uses regression analysis, which led to the discovery that managerial efficiency and revenue efficiency tend to have negative effects on banks. This study is useful for the thesis on "The potential effect of privatisation of government banks: Case study of IDBI Bank" as it provides a comparative analysis of private sector banks and public sector banks, which helps to identify the impact of privatisation ation in India's banking sector. A similar comparative

study was conducted by Pandian(2020) which analysed the impact of mergers on nationalised commercial banks in India from 2000 to . The aspects considered by the author include return on equity, return on assets, earnings per share and earnings per employee. The banks considered for the study are IDBI Bank, State Bank of India and Bank of Baroda. The results suggest that mergers have both positive and negative effects on banks. For example, mergers have a positive impact on earnings per share and earnings per employee. On the other hand, return on equity, return on assets and profit ratio are negatively affected by a merger.

Bertay et al.(2020) studies recent trends in bank privatization to analyse its economic impact on the growth and development of a country. The period considered by the authors is twenty-five years and the results of the study suggest that over the last twenty-five years, the trend towards the privatisation of banks has grown in popularity and has become much more frequent. The authors also found evidence to support their assertion that privatisation of banks became more common after the global financial crisis in countries such as India and China, which have developing markets. Privatisation trends also suggested that the capital market sales that led to privatisation were predominantly state-owned. The reason for this was the visibly poor asset quality of public sector banks, and empirical evidence has shown that performance after privatisation has largely improved. However, the evidence also suggests that there is considerable scope for improvement in banking procedures in the post-privatisation period. The three main conclusions of this study are as follows:

- Privatised banks move towards the traditional banking model
- Privatised banks are increasing lending excessively, but with negative consequences for distribution.
- Banks that were recapitalised before privatisation are operating successfully after privatisation.

Finally, Sabir and Qayyum(2018) examine the impact of privatisation on profit efficiency using examples from commercial banks in Pakistan. The Pakistani banking sector has been privatised for almost two decades and has changed from its previous nationalisation status. The authors used the stochastic frontier true effect and random true effect. In addition, the authors examine the subject from the perspective of intermediation, and the data

is collected from twenty-two commercial banks in Pakistan. The authors consider the period from 1995 to 2014. The analytical method is empirical in nature. The results of the study suggest that foreign banks have higher profit margin than commercial banks, though commercial banks are about 73 percent efficient. This is irrespective of the ownership of commercial banks . The second conclusion of this thesis suggests that commercial banks, irrespective of ownership, are much more cost efficient . The authors explored the areas of profit efficiency and cost efficiency of banks to arrive at this conclusion

2.4 Potential impact of the privatisation of state-owned banks

In the study aimed at analysing e the impact of privatisation ation of government banks, the most important aspect is to recognise both the positive and the negative impact of this privatisation on the banking sector. In the proposed thesis, observations are focused on the banking sector in India through a case study of the recently privatised IDBI bank ed. N umerous studies have been conducted on the same subject, examining a variety of effects of privatisation ation. Some of these effects are mentioned below, as defined by Ramanadham ,(2019) who focused on the impact of privatisation ation in developing countries:

❖ Positive impact

- Greater consumer satisfaction
- Improving customer service
- More benefits
- Easy mitigation process for non-performing assets
- Aids to competitive advantage
- Improvement in the rate of foreign investment and the degree of infusion
- Creating more job opportunities

❖ Negative impact

- Questions relating to the right to information or RTI
- Accessibility issues
- No benefits for disadvantaged groups in society

- Rural areas worst affected in terms of banking services after privatisation

The privatisation of banks can be seen as a godsend, as it allows to offer better customer service while providing all the necessary assistance that a customer needs. It also helps banks to grow, as profit margins for private banks are significantly higher. However, as private banks do not have special margins or quotas preserved for the lower classes, this becomes a burden, and banks end up becoming inaccessible to them.

Reinsberg *et al.*(2020) stated in their study that privatisation leads to corruption in the system. They studied in detail the case of the International Monetary Fund (IMF), in which state-owned enterprises are responsible for limiting corruption. The data analysed are those from more than 140 developing countries between 1982 and 2014. The results of this study suggest that the privatisation of state-owned enterprises has a "detrimental" impact on corruption. The recommendation is to avoid any type of large-scale privatisation.

Shaban and James(2018) also study the impact of ownership change on banking performance in relation to risk exposure using a sample of 60 commercial banks in Indonesia. The results suggest that public banks are less profitable and more vulnerable to risk than private banks. Vo and Nguyen(2018) also studied the banking structure and the efficiency of banks in terms of privatisation. They studied a sample of twenty-six commercial banks in Vietnam between 1999 and 2015. The results suggest that during mergers or restructuring of banks, banking efficiency slows down. Estrin and Pelletier(2018) conducted an empirical study of privatisation in developing countries in order to understand its distributional impact. The results of this study indicate a positive impact of privatisation on the promotion of equity in developing countries. Boubakri *et al.*(2020) also conducted a similar study at (Shaban & James, 2018), focusing on post-privatisation and risk factors, as in Shaban and James (2018). The results of both studies suggest that risk is much higher under state governance.

According to a critical study led by Brochado(2018), the author poses the question of whether public banks are a necessary evil, and the study's conclusions are based on the impact of public authority or state ownership in banks. The study was conducted in the eurozone, and the period considered is five years, from 2011 to 2016. This thesis evaluates several studies predecessors to ensure the best possible understanding of the issue raised by

the author. The idea for the study arose from an in-depth study of various economic moments, such as the 2007-2008 economic crisis, and how public banks and other financial firms dealt with the same situation. The author used the random effects model, and the findings of the thesis indicate that public ownership of banks led to a decrease in the efficiency and profitability of banks, according to the evidence gathered by the researcher. Furthermore, the study suggests that risk factors depend entirely on the country location of the bank in question, irrespective of ownership. Finally, this thesis focuses on the mechanism that will be most appropriate for dealing with unprecedented crisis situations.

It can therefore be seen that bank privatisation has been profitable, as margins have shown significant growth that was previously lacking. It was also seen as a bad thing for a long time, but privatisation has proved beneficial not only for businesses, but also for customers. The risk factors that banks possess may differ from place to place and do not change due to the ownership model. Banks are not that privatised have a lower profit margin, even though they run the same risk as private banks.

According to the literature available, it has been noted that the privatisation of industries has had an impact on almost all sectors, but has failed to do so in the banking sector.

Research gaps

After conducting exhaustive research on the related literature, it was found that the studies conducted by (Jegadeeshwaran & Basuvaraj, 2019; Kumar et al., 2020b; Boubakri et al., 2020), and others have a significant gap with the proposed thesis on "Potential Effect of Privatisation of Government Banks: Case study of IDBI Bank". The present study focuses on the impact of privatisation, in particular on the banking sector in relation to the industrial sector as well. A comprehensive understanding of the related literature validates the pronounced gap between the existing literature and the proposed thesis. The existing literature on privatisation addresses its overall impact on the different sectors, but the gap between industrial privatisation and banking sector privatisation has not yet been noted. This research highlights the different outcomes that can be expected if banking sectors are privatised rather than state-owned. The gap in the literature helps the researcher to focus on the sections that have not yet been implemented.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This study focuses on the effects of privatisation of government banks, with the Indian Commercial Bank, IDBI, being the source of a case study. The research is exploratory in nature and the type of data analysed is quantitative in nature. The source of data considered in this research will also be the primary data source . The aim of this chapter is first and foremost to describe the methods used to carry out the research. The research methodology of any study can be considered the backbone of the research, as its function is to provide the researcher with the blueprints for the research procedures (Basias & Pollalis, 2018) . The following subtopics considered in this chapter of the study will be explained using the necessary details and steps of the research methodology for the current research (Kothari, 2020) .

3.2 Research philosophy

At the start of any research work, it is imperative that the researcher considers a set of beliefs and reasoning that will come into play in the way the data is collected and in turn interpreted. This set of beliefs or reasoning is known as the research philosophy of a study. It is an essential sub-chapter of the study as it helps the researcher to identify the potential reasons for and, more importantly, the scope of the topic chosen for the study (Moon et al., 2019) . In addition, research philosophy helps the researcher develop a unique perspective on the study topic and provides the motivation to commit to conducting the research effectively in order to reach an ideal conclusion. In practice, four main types of research philosophy are used. They are as follows -

Positivism: This type of philosophy focuses primarily on the analysis of quantitative data to reach an objective conclusion. Researchers who opt for this research philosophy generally focus on identifying changes in the social world.

Interpretation: In the case of research based on an interpretivist philosophy , the researcher's task is to examine and analyse the data collected in order to interpret the data in their own terms, bearing in mind the objective of the most effective interpretation, which will lead to ideal results and conclusions.

Pragmatism: The research philosophy of pragmatism is an amalgam of positivism and interpretation, as in , which is ideal when working with a combination of qualitative and quantitative types of data. In the case of pragmatism, researchers opt for a more philosophical approach to the study of a given subject. It is therefore a research philosophy popular with researchers who see as the best way of achieving the research objectives they have set themselves.

Realism: The realist philosophy is considered to be a more humanitarian approach to research . It gives researchers many opportunities to play freely with the ideas and theories that arise in their own minds.

In the case of the research on the theme "Potential effect of the privatisation of public banks with IDBI Bank as a case study", , the research philosophy chosen by the researcher is the **positivist** philosophy because the essence of the study depends on the investigation, estimation and analysis of quantitative data which must be collected from primary and secondary sources.

3.3 Research approach

The research approach of any study refers to the planning and formulation of procedures for conducting the research. A pre-planned approach helps the researcher to conduct the study more efficiently and facilitates the achievement of results (Schmitz et al., 2015) . The researcher's planning and procedures, as defined in the research approach, help to validate the researcher's authenticity. In practice, the research approach can be divided into three distinct categories:

- a) Deductive approach.
- b) Inductive approach.
- c) Abductive approach.

The best possible research approach in the case of the study "Potential Effect of Privatisation of Public Banks with IDBI Bank as a Case Study" will therefore be the **deductive** approach because the study requires the researcher to study the quantitative data and then test the hypotheses that emerge from the analysis of the data (Pandey & Pandey, 2021) . Using a deductive approach also implies that the researcher opts to study existing

theories and interpretations to formulate their own unique and nuanced perspectives on the constituent elements of the object of study.

3.4 Research design

The research design of a study is based on the overall strategy applied during the study. The design helps the researcher to know the steps to be taken to conduct the research (Jilcha Sileyew, 2020). Research design can be of several types, namely descriptive, experimental, correlational and case studies . The title of the topic "Potential effect of privatisation of public banks with IDBI Bank as a case study" clearly shows that the appropriate design for this research is a **case study** research design. Therefore, it is a case study based research in which the researcher will examine the data related to IDBI Bank in order to understand the impact of privatisation of public banks, in line with the purpose of the study. Based on this subject , the constituents of the dependent variables are employees and banking sector. On the other hand, the set of independent variables consists of employee satisfaction, employee reliability, employee productivity, banking efficiency, profitability, quality of banking services, capital management, management efficiency and risk management.

3.5 Data collection and sampling methods :

3.51 Study framework and data collection.

This study required primary data to be collected directly from the source. Thus, IDBI Bank employees in India. However, the massive number of employees working in all the branches of the bank in India means that approaching all the employees is not an easy task. Therefore, to facilitate the work of the researcher, it is necessary that a sample of employees is chosen as representative of the entire workforce (Etikan, 2017) . The study setting lends itself particularly well to the collection of data from people employed in management and clerical functions. The employees sampled will preferably come from all available branches in order to avoid geographical variables. There were also no restrictions on age or gender in the population. The data will be collected using online questionnaires . These questionnaires will be distributed to all employees, but given that not all will respond and that it is necessary to eliminate those who will not answer the questions accurately, a minimum number of 300 employees has been set as the sample size (de Melo et al., 2015).

3.5.2 Data analysis tools.

The data will be analysed after the sample data has been collected and coded. The sample data is collected through responses to questionnaires circulated online among IDBI Bank employees. The data will only be analysed once the exploratory graphical analysis has been completed (Tu, 2018). The Graphic analysis will be carried out in establishing the hypotheses. The hypotheses were tested using different data analysis tools . The objective is to establish an accepted hypothesis. Once the accepted hypothesis has been estimated, a chi-squared analysis technique must be used to establish the appropriate relationship between the components of the independent variables and those of the dependent variables.

3.6 Ethical considerations :

A set of principles that govern the researcher's actions when conducting research from ethical considerations in research (Ketefian, 2015) . As the research did not involve any health-related studies, the health of the participants was not put at risk . The researcher made sure not to include any sensitive information about the organisation. Finally, the researcher insisted on the impartiality of the participants in the study and gave priority to the analysis of the data collected from them in an impartial manner . See appendix 1

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the researcher presents the results of the quantitative data. Firstly, the information was entered into an Excel spreadsheet before being exported to SPSS 20.0. The present study was analysed using SPSS software. The sample size for the study was 63 participants. The internal consistency of the data was calculated using Cronbach's alpha. Descriptive statistical analyses were carried out for each element of the factor. Correlation was used to determine the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Regression was used to determine the association between the independent variables and the dependent variables.

Table 4.1 .1: Frequency of sex

	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Men	29	46.0
Woman	34	54.0
Total	63	100.0

Table 4.1.1 shows the frequency of gender differences. A majority (54.0%) of respondents were female, while 46.0% of respondents were male. According to the pie chart below, the gender distribution is predominantly female and male, but no other (o) gender is represented among the respondents.

Table 4.1.2 : Age frequency

	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
21-30	4	6.35
31-40	42	66.67
41-50	12	19.05
More than 50	5	7.93
Total	63	100.0

Table 4.1.2 shows the frequency of age. The majority of respondents (66.67%) were aged 31 to 40, followed by 19.05% aged 41 to 50, 7.93% aged over 50 and 6.35% aged 21 to 30.

Figure 4.1.2(a): Percentage for age

Table 4.1.3: Frequency of level of education

	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Secondary school	0	0
UG	0	0
PG	63	100.0
Doctorate	0	0
Total	63	100.0

Table 4.1.3 shows the frequency of level of education. All respondents have completed PG.

Table 4.1.4: Frequency of designation

	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Executive Vice-President	2	3.2
Deputy Director	34	54.0
Office workers	6	9.5
Frame	1	1.6
Manager	19	30.1
RM	1	1.6
Total	63	100.0

Table 4.1.4 shows the frequency of designation. The majority of respondents (54%) are assistant directors and 30.1% are directors, while 9.5% and 3.2% are clerical staff

and assistant general managers respectively, and the remaining executive and managerial positions (1.6%) are held by clerical staff.

Figure 4.1.4(a) : Percentage of designation

Table 4.1.5: Frequency of the experiment

	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1-3 years	1	1.6
3-7 years	16	25.4
7-10 years	19	30.1
More than 10 years	27	42.9
Total	63	100.0

Table 4.1.5 shows the frequency of experience. The majority of respondents (42.9%) have more than 10 years' experience, followed by 30.1% of respondents with between 7 and 10 years' experience, 25.4% of respondents with between 3 and 7 years' experience and 1.6% of respondents with between 1 and 3 years' experience. The majority of respondents have between 7 and more than 10 years' experience, totalling 73%, which is also the youngest staff.

Figure 4.1.5(a): Percentage for the experiment

Table 4.1.6: Areas of risk that the bank deals with frequently

	Frequency	Percentage
Credit risk	45	71.4
Liquidity risk	1	1.6
Market risk	16	25.4
Solvency risk	1	1.6
Total	63	100.0

Table 4.1.6 shows which areas of risk the bank often faces. The majority of respondents (71.4%) believe that the risk is related to credit, 25.4% to the market and 1.6% to liquidity and solvency. The majority of 71.4% of banks often deal with credit risk

Table 4.1.7: The riskiest areas in your banking activities

	Frequency	Percentage
Consumer loans	16	25.4
Property loans	16	25.4
Securities-linked loans	31	49.2
Total	63	100.0

Table 4.1.7 explains the areas of highest risk in their banking business process . Approximately 49.2% of respondents felt that the highest risk was in securities lending. In

addition, 25.4% of respondents found the highest risk in consumer and property-related lending - .

Table 4.1.8: Risk bank inflation target

	Frequency	Percentage
1%	5	7.9
2%	3	4.8
3%	14	22.2
Don't know	41	65.1
Total	63	100.0

Table 4.1.8 shows the banks' inflation targets. In majority of 65.1% of respondents said they did not know, followed by 22.2% of respondents (3% and 7.9%); 4.8% of respondents said the inflation target was of 1% and 2% respectively.

Table 4.1.9: If there is a risk of inflation exceeding the inflation target, what should the Risk Bank do?

	Frequency	Percentage
Don't know	34	54.0
Do nothing	11	17.4
Reducing the repo rate	15	23.8
Increase the repo rate	3	4.8
Total	63	100.0

Table 4.1.9 shows the response of bank when exceeds the inflation target. In the majority (54%) of respondents replied that they were unaware, and then 23.8% of respondents replied lower the repo rate, 17.4% of respondents did nothing and 4.8% of respondents increased the repo rate. In The majority (54%) of respondents were unaware of the risk of inflation exceeding the inflation target.

Table 4.1.10: If the nominal interest rate is 5% and expected inflation is 2%, what will the real interest rate be (approximately)?

	Frequency	Percentage
2.50%	1	1.6
3%	6	9.5
7%	16	25.4
Don't know	40	63.5
Total	63	100.0

Table 4.1.10 shows the increase in the real interest rate when the nominal interest rate is 5% and expected inflation is 2%. A majority of 63.5% of respondents answered don't know, followed by 25.4% of respondents reported 7%, 9.5% of respondents answered 3%, and 1.6% of respondents answered that 2.50% was the increase in the real interest rate.

Table 4.1.11: A savings product in which you receive a guaranteed amount at maturity, and whose return follows the equity market, is called :

	Frequency	Percentage
Don't know	19	30.2
Equity funds	1	1.6
Equity-linked security	39	61.9
Hedge funds	4	6.3
Total	63	100.0

Table 4.1.11 shows the savings products for which you will receive a guaranteed amount at maturity. Some 61.9% of respondents said that these were equity-linked securities, 30.2% did not know, 6.3% hedge funds and 1.6% equity funds.

Table 4.1.12: Mutual funds have different levels of risk; which of these types of mutual fund is generally considered to have the highest risk?

	Frequency	Percentage
Bond funds	2	3.2
Don't know	18	28.6
Equity funds	43	68.2
Total	63	100.0

Table 4.1.12 shows which types of mutual funds are generally considered to present the highest risk. The majority of respondents (68.2%) consider equity funds to present the highest risk, followed by 28.6% of respondents who do not know and 3.2% of respondents who consider bond funds to present the highest risk.

Table 4.1.13: Reliability analysis

	Number of items	Average	Cronbach's Alpha
Employee satisfaction	10	4.36	0.823
Customer integration	8	4.1	0.625
Supplier integration	8	4.3	0.860
Internal integration	10	4.34	0.891
Internal control	8	4.31	0.802
Bank efficiency	5	4.56	0.873
Reliability axis	5	4.45	0.804
Response axis	5	4.18	0.701
Focus on the efficiency of service providers	4	4.43	0.856
Access axis	4	4.39	0.823
Focus on tact	4	4.45	0.863
Axis of communication	5	4.5	0.843
Credibility axis	4	4.41	0.819
Safety hub	4	3.95	0.576
Sympathy axis	5	4.32	0.828
The emphasis is on tangible physical and human aspects	5	4.33	0.755
Capital management	7	3.96	0.787
Management efficiency	8	4.46	0.859
Attitude to risk	2	4.75	0.714
Financial performance	6	4.02	0.831

The study used reliability analysis for each multi-item scale using Cronbach's alpha. The table above shows the results of the reliability analysis and the descriptive statistics for each variable. Overall, the study reported moderate reliability with alpha ranging from 0.576 to 0.891, demonstrating that the scale has moderate reliability.

Table 4.2.1 shows the Pearson correlation analysis. The correlation analysis shows the linearity between the variables, not the strength of the association between the dependent and independent variables, represented by the r and p values, where r represents the degree of correlation and p the significance level. The table clearly shows that employee satisfaction has a significant positive linear relationship with financial performance ($r=0.566$, $p<0.01$). Employee productivity has a significant positive linear relationship with financial performance ($r=0.695$, $p<0.01$). Bank efficiency shows a significant positive linear relationship with financial performance ($r=0.447$, $p<0.01$). The quality of banking services shows a significant positive linear relationship with financial performance ($r=0.451$, $p<0.01$). Capital management shows a significant positive linear relationship with financial performance ($r=0.622$, $p<0.01$). The' shows a significant positive linear relationship with financial performance ($r=0.717$, $p<0.01$). Risk attitude shows a significant positive linear relationship with financial performance ($r=0.382$, $p<0.01$). We therefore conclude that the hypothesis

H₀₁: There is a significant relationship between employee satisfaction, employee productivity, bank efficiency, quality of banking services, capital management, management efficiency, attitude to risk and financial performance.

Regression :

H₀₂ : Employee satisfaction has a significant impact on financial performance.

H₁₂: There is no significant impact of staff satisfaction on finance.

Table 4.2.2: Association between employee satisfaction and financial performance

	Non-standardised coefficients		Square R	t-value	p-value
	Beta	SE			
(Constant)	0.792	0.604	0.32	1.309	0.195
Employee satisfaction	0.739	0.138		5.36	0.000**

Dependent variable: Financial performance, **p<0.01

The associations between employee satisfaction and financial performance are presented in table 4.2.2. In the regression model, employee satisfaction is considered as an independent variable, while financial performance is considered as a dependent variable. The significant value (p-value<0.05) clearly shows that employee satisfaction ($\beta=0.739$, $t=5.36$, $p<0.001$) has an impact on positive financial performance. Furthermore, 32% of the variation in financial performance depends on employee satisfaction (R-square=0.320), so there is a link between employee satisfaction and financial performance. We therefore conclude that the

H₀₂: The impact of employee satisfaction on financial performance is significant.

H₀₃: Bank efficiency has a significant impact on financial performance.

H₁₃: There is no significant impact of the bank's efficiency on the financial sector.

Table 4.2.3: Association between bank efficiency and financial performance

	Non-standardised coefficients		Square R	t-value	p-value
	Beta	SE			
(Constant)	1.562	0.631	0.200	2.475	0.160
Bank efficiency	0.539	0.138		3.907	0.000**

Dependent variable: Financial performance, **p<0.01

The associations between bank efficiency and financial performance are presented in table 4.2.3. In the regression model, bank efficiency was considered as an independent

variable, while financial performance was considered as a dependent variable. The significant value ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$) clearly shows that bank efficiency ($\beta = 0.539$, $t = 3.907$, $p < 0.001$) affects positively financial performance. Furthermore, 20% of the variation in financial performance depends on bank efficiency ($R\text{-square} = 0.200$), so there is a link between bank efficiency and financial performance. We therefore conclude that the

H₀₃: The impact of bank efficiency on financial performance is significant.

H₀₄: Capital management has a significant impact on financial performance.

H₁₄: There is no significant impact of capital management on financial performance.

Table 4.2.4: Association between capital management and financial performance

	Non-standardised coefficients		Square R	t-value	p-value
	Beta	SE			
(Constant)	1.590	0.394	0.387	4.031	0.000
Capital management	0.612	0.099		6.212	0.000**

Dependent variable: Financial performance, ** $p < 0.01$

The associations between capital management and financial performance are presented in table 4.2.4. In the regression model, capital management was considered as an independent variable, while financial performance was considered as a dependent variable. The significant value ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$) clearly shows that capital management ($\beta = 0.612$, $t = 6.212$, $p < 0.001$) affects positively financial performance. Furthermore, 39% of the variation in financial performance depends on capital management ($R\text{-square} = 0.387$). There is therefore a link between capital management and financial performance. We therefore conclude that the

H₀₄: The impact of capital management on financial performance is significant.

H₀₅: Management efficiency has a significant impact on financial performance.

H₁₅: There is no significant impact of management efficiency on financial performance.

Table 4.2.5: Association between management effectiveness and financial performance

	Non-standardised coefficients	Square R	t-value	p-value
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	Beta	SE			
(Constant)	0.036	0.498	0.514	.071	0.943
Management efficiency	0.892	0.111		8.025	0.000**

Dependent variable: Financial performance, **p<0.01

The associations between management effectiveness and financial performance are presented in Table 4.2.5. In the regression model, management effectiveness was considered as an independent variable, while financial performance was considered as a dependent variable. The significance statistical was greater than 0.05. This provides significant evidence against the null hypothesis, given that the null hypothesis has less than a 5% chance of being correct (and the results are random). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was accepted. The significant value (p-value<0.05) clearly shows that management effectiveness ($\beta=0.892$, $t=8.025$, $p<0.001$) affects the positive financial performance of . Furthermore, 51% of the variation in financial performance depends on management efficiency (R-squared=0.514). There is therefore a link between management effectiveness and financial performance. We therefore conclude that the

H₀₅ : The impact of management effectiveness on financial performance is significant.

H₀₆ : Risk attitude has a significant impact on financial performance.

H₁₆ : There is no significant impact of attitude to risk on financial performance.

Table 4.2.6: Association between attitude to risk and financial performance

	Non-standardised coefficients		Square R	t-value	p-value
	Beta	SE			
(Constant)	1.858	0.672	0.146	2.764	0.008
Attitude to risk	0.455	0.141		3.227	0.002**

Dependent variable: Financial performance, ** $p < 0.01$

The association between a ttitudes towards risk and financial performance is presented in table 4.2.6. In the regression model, a ttitude towards risk was s considered as an independent variable , while financial performance was s considered as a dependent variable. The significant value ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$) clearly shows that attitude to risk ($\beta = 0.455$, $t = 3.227$, $p < 0.001$) has an impact on the positive financial performance. In addition, 15% of the variation in financial performance depends on a ttitude to risk ($R\text{-square} = 0.146$). There is therefore a link between a ttitudes to risk and financial performance. We therefore conclude that the hypothesis

H₀₆ : The impact of risk attitude on financial performance is significant.

Table 4.2.7: Association between customer integration, supplier integration, internal integration, internal control and financial performance using stepwise regression

Model		Non-standardised coefficients		Square R	t-value	P value
		Beta	SE			
1	(Constant)	0.655	0.542	0.389	1.208	.232
	Supplier integration	0.784	0.126		6.234	.000**
2	(Constant)	-0.484	0.609	0.483	-.795	.430
	Supplier integration	0.582	0.132		4.426	.000**
	Internal control	0.464	0.140		3.309	.002**

Dependent variable: Financial performance, ** $p < 0.01$

The associations between employee productivity and financial performance are presented in table 4.2.7. In Model 1, supplier integration is considered as an independent variable , while financial performance is considered as a dependent variable . The significant value ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$) clearly shows that supplier integration ($\beta = 0.784$, $t = 6.234$, $p < 0.001$) affects financial performance positively . Furthermore, 38.9% of the variation in financial performance depends on supplier integration ($R\text{-square} = 0.389$). In M odel 2, supplier

integration and internal control are considered as independent variables, while financial performance is considered as dependent variable. The significant value (p -value <0.05) clearly shows that supplier integration ($\beta=0.582$, $t=4.429$, $p<0.001$) and internal control ($\beta=0.464$, $t=3.309$, $p<0.001$) have a positive impact on financial performance. Furthermore, 48.3% of the variation in financial performance depends on supplier integration and internal control (R -square=0.483). There is therefore a link between employee productivity and financial performance.

Table 4.2.8 Association between the quality of banking services and financial performance using stepwise regression

Model		Non-standardised coefficients		Square R	t-value	P value
		Beta	SE			
1	(Constant)	1.222	0.553	0.297	2.209	0.031
	Sympathy axis	0.647	0.127		5.077	0.000**

Dependent variable: Financial performance, ** $p<0.01$

The association between banking service quality and financial performance using the stepwise method is presented in table 4.2.8 . In the regression model, the sympathy axis was considered as an independent variable , while financial performance was considered as a dependent variable. The significant value (p -value <0.05) clearly shows that the sympathy axis ($\beta=0.647$, $t=5.077$, $p<0.001$) has a positive impact on financial performance. Furthermore, 29.7% of the variation in financial performance depends on the sympathy axis (R -square=0.297). There is therefore a link between the sympathy axis and financial performance .

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Discussion

5.1.1 Interpretation of the survey

The survey contained quantitative data, which we reinterpreted using SPSS software, in line with the analysis in this study. The sample size chosen for the survey was 63 (see table 4.1.1), and the internal consistency of the data was calculated using Cronbach's alpha. The survey includes 12 questions which help to understand in depth the effects of the privatisation of IDBI Bank. The first question is linked to gender, which makes it possible to interpret that out of 63 respondents, 29 men and 34 women took part in the survey.

Table 4.1.2 shows the majority of respondents aged between 31 and 40 who took part in the survey. Table 4.1.3 highlights the educational qualifications of the respondents, and the survey reveals that all 63 respondents belong to a higher education level. Table 4.1.4 shows their position within IDBI Bank. Most of the respondents are designated as assistant managers. This means that employees' prospects are hampered by a lack of skills and the restructuring of the company, as the previous demographic survey showed. Table 4.1.5 shows the frequency of experience: 42.9% of employees have been associated with the bank for 10 years. This proportion indicates that they are tolerated by the company and are most likely unable to obtain an acceptable job in another organisation. Table 4.1.6 represents the region of risk encountered in banking transactions, with the majority of votes cast for market risk. This table shows that IDBI is extremely vulnerable to sudden changes in interest rates, recessions, commodity prices and share prices. Table 4.1.8 represents the risk associated with the bank's inflation target, which is not known to the majority of respondents. A lack of knowledge may hinder the achievement of 'successful' industrial countries that do not have an inflation target. In table 4.1.9, the majority of respondents replied that they did not know, and 23% referred to lowering the repo rate when inflation exceeds the inflation target. In this context, the increase in interest rates means a slow ignition accompanied by a reduction in economic growth.

In table 4.1.10, 25.4% of respondents think that if the nominal interest rate is 5%, the expected ignition may be 2%. In this case, the interest rate should be increased to 7%. In

this case, the interest rate should be 3% because real interest rates play an important role in inflation, which can lead to negative territory.

Tables 4.1.11 and 4.1.12 represent product-related questions, which include bank and third-party products, to determine the level of risk of different products, of which 61.9% think that equity-linked securities have the highest guaranteed amount at maturity, and 68.2% think that equity funds are the riskiest of mutual funds, respectively. Equities are strongly influenced by market movements; therefore, equity funds may face currency risks due to exchange rate fluctuations.

5.1.2 Interpretation of the reliability analysis

The reliability of each team was analysed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The study revealed moderate reliability, with alpha coefficients ranging from 0.576 to 0.891. Other correlations between the coefficients were formulated to examine whether the two variables agree. The independent and dependent variables are presented, revealing linearity between the variables. The results indicate a positive relationship between employee productivity, banking performance, capital management, management efficiency, attitude to risk and financial performance. This means that the performance of the internal organisation is effective when the independent variables mentioned increase; however, the strength of the association cannot be interpreted from this relationship.

5.1.3 Interpretation of the regression analysis

As far as employee satisfaction is concerned, the null hypothesis proved to be highly significant, implying that a high degree of employee satisfaction has a positive impact on financial performance. Similarly, the other three variables - bank efficiency, capital management, management efficiency and attitude to risk - are positively related to financial performance. The independent variables of employee satisfaction, bank efficiency and capital management have a less than moderate impact on financial performance, with values of 0.32, 0.200 and 0.387, respectively. Given that the p-value in the regression between capital management, bank efficiency, management effectiveness, employee satisfaction and financial performance is less than 0.001, it can be inferred that the former has a significant and positive impact on the independent variable. A p-value of 0.001 indicates that the null hypothesis is true. The p-value for the regression between risk attitude and financial performance was greater than 0.001, i.e. 0.002. This result implies that risk attitude has a very small impact on

the independent variable. If the dependent variable affects financial performance, due to the linear correlation, increasing the efficiency of the former will help to improve the efficiency of the latter, but to a minimal extent.

5.2 Conclusion

5.2.1 Conclusion

The conclusion is the final chapter of the thesis and serves to summarise all the findings of the research. After an in-depth analysis, it can be concluded that the banking sector has always played an integral role in the country's economy, helping to pump and maintain the flow of money. The problem identified lies in the ownership of government banks that are being transformed into private companies, forcing existing employees to have different professional lives.

5.2.2 Link with objectives

It is essential to link each chapter of this dissertation to various aspects of the literature review. The es objectives of this study are as follows:

Objective 1: "Identify the advantages of working in government and business".

The objective can be well derived from the two aspects of the literature review which provide insights into the trends of privatisation ation practiced within Indian government banks, and the potential effects of privatisation ation within government banks.

Objective 2: "Understand the differences between the working environment of a government and that of a private company".

This objective is linked to the two facets of the literature review which highlights the negative and positive impacts of privatisation ation among government banks and the trends in privatisation ation among government banks operating in India.

Objective 3: "Analyse the parameters of the changes facing employees as a result of changing jobs".

The aspect of the literature assessment that highlights the potential impact of privatisation ation among Indian government banks demonstrates the characteristics of

change that workers regularly face due to the transfer of concerns. Therefore , this can be successfully linked to the above objective.

Objective 4: "Examine the impact of changes on employees".

The section on the literature which deals with the potential consequences of privatisation ation of India's state-owned banks reveals the characteristics of the changes that workers regularly face as a result of transition. Therefore, , this point can be successfully linked to a previously specified objective.

Objective 5: "To recommend ways of facilitating change and helping employees get used to the new environment".

No aspect of the section of the literature review provides recommendations for the above objective. Consequently, no link could be established with this objective in the literature review.

5.3 Recommendations

Recommendation 1: Improve recruitment procedures and empower staff

It is essential that Government of India banks move towards privatisation to understand the roles and responsibilities that best match their external and internal candidates (Alsafadi & Altahat, 2021). In this way, banks managing can give the team as a whole, as well as the recruitment process, a boost in terms of inefficiency.

Recommendation 2: Improve employee satisfaction and commitment

Public sector employees enjoy a number of advantages over private sector employees. Private banks have a higher retention rate, leading to lower staff engagement (Bowen & Lawler, 1994). Therefore, rapid appraisals can help to demonstrate employee happiness and commitment. This strategy also reduces the risk of employee retention compared to the benefits offered to them.

Recommendation 3: Focus on managerial implications

It is important for the IDBI bank manager to build successful relationships with the community in order to gain support from potential customers and employees, especially during the privatisation transformation (Gowri & Mariammal, 2019). In addition, if the bank manager makes sure to obtain a licence from the central bank, employees will be less fearful and will cooperate more with the bank's activities.

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Appendix 1

POTENTIAL IMPACT OF THE PRIVATISATION OF STATE-OWNED BANKS WITH THE CASE STUDY OF IDBI BANK

Cover letter for the survey questionnaire

Dear participant,

I'm continuing my Master's thesis. "I am pursuing my Master's thesis entitled "Potential Effect of Privatization of Government Banks with IDBI Bank as a case study". Your opinion on the factors influencing employee satisfaction, employee productivity, bank efficiency, profitability, quality of banking services, etc. on financial performance would be very much appreciated.

The survey is simple and takes less than 25-30 minutes. I **would be very** grateful for your professional involvement if you would complete the survey as soon as possible. Participation is entirely voluntary, but once again **I need your support** to make this effort a success.

Rest assured that your reply will be treated with in the strictest confidence. Under no circumstances will your information be made available to any person or organisation. If you have any questions about , please do not hesitate to contact me at c0032513@my.shu.ac.uk. T and thank you in advance for any suggestions you may have.

Yours sincerely

Ashwani Kumar Tripathi

QUESTIONNAIRE

Section I: Personal information

S.no	Personal information
1.	Gender Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/> Do not wish to specify <input type="checkbox"/>
2.	Age (in years) 18-20 <input type="checkbox"/> 21-30 <input type="checkbox"/> 31-40 <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> More than 50 <input type="checkbox"/>
3.	Level of education High school <input type="checkbox"/> UG <input type="checkbox"/> PG <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
4.	Designation
5.	Experience (in years) 0-1 year <input type="checkbox"/> 1-3 years <input type="checkbox"/> 3-7 years <input type="checkbox"/> 7-10 years <input type="checkbox"/> more than 10 years <input type="checkbox"/>

Section II: Employee satisfaction

Employee satisfaction factors include the following statements on a 5-point rating scale ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree", with a score of 1 to 5 respectively.

(1) Strongly disagree, (2) d disagree, (3) n neutral, (4) a agree, (5) Strongly agree

S.no	Employee satisfaction	1	2	3	4	5
1.	The bank's supervisor respects his subordinates	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	The working environment in the bank is good.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	The Bank has good working conditions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	The atmosphere within the Bank is joyful	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5.	The decor of the bank building is welcoming.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7.	The Bank respects its employees	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8.	The director is always ready to give positive advice.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
9.	The Bank offers good safety conditions at work	<input type="checkbox"/>				
10.	The Bank provides good working equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section III: Employee productivity

Employee productivity factors are presented in the following statements on a 5-point rating scale ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree", with a score of 1 to 5 respectively.

(1) Strongly disagree, (2) d disagree, (3) n neutral, (4) a agree, (5) Strongly agree

Sno	Employee productivity	1	2	3	4	5
	Customer integration					

1.	The bank seeks to build relationships with its customers and to	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	The bank may seek to obtain a good RC, but not to get involved.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	The level of networking between banks is satisfactory	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	The bank regularly assesses the value of its customer relationships.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5.	Planning, forecasting and innovation are carried out in collaboration at this bank.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6.	We strive to meet our customers' needs.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7.	We regularly measure customer satisfaction.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8.	The bank follows up with customers to obtain feedback.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Supplier integration						
1.	The bank maintains cooperative relationships with its suppliers.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	The bank shares its production plans with its suppliers.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	The bank maintains close communication with suppliers regarding quality considerations and design changes.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	The bank is setting up rapid ordering systems with its main suppliers.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5.	Our main supplier shares its production schedule with the bank.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6.	The level of information exchange between the bank and its main supplier via our information network.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7.	The bank helps its main suppliers to improve their processes in order to better meet its needs.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8.	The bank strives to establish long-term relationships with its suppliers.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Internal integration						
1.	The bank integrates data between internal functions.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	The integration of real time and communication is instilled in all the internal functions of the bank's departments.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	Bank departments share ideas, information and/or resources.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	The use of regular interdepartmental meetings within the bank's internal functions.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5.	The bank's departments take the technical and operational decisions for the project together.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6.	The bank's functions work together to resolve conflicts between them when they arise.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7.	Bank performance indicators encourage rational trade-offs between customer service and operating costs.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8.	The bank's departments help each other to carry out their tasks as efficiently as possible.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

9.	The bank's departments work together to achieve these objectives.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
10.	All the company's departments interact with each other.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Internal control						
1.	The bank uses the knowledge acquired or documented in planning supply chain strategy, producing services according to customer needs, managing customer orders, logistics, invoicing and supply chain development.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	The bank has an impact on the flow of liquidity throughout the supply chain.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	Integrated and transparent information systems encourage collaboration between the bank and its supply chain partners.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	Senior management defines expectations in terms of company operations and internal controls.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5.	Management is responsible for defining governance, risk management and compliance policies, processes and procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6.	The internal auditors provide the Board of Directors with assurance on management's performance and tasks.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7.	Responsibilities are divided between members of staff (so that no single employee has the power to execute two or more conflicting sensitive transactions), thus maintaining an appropriate segregation of duties.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8.	The bank has integrated its internal controls into a computerised system.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section IV: Bank efficiency

The bank's effectiveness factors include the following statements on a 5-point rating scale ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree", with a score of 1 to 5 respectively.

(1) Strongly disagree, (2) d disagree, (3) n neutral, (4) a agree, (5) Strongly agree

Sno	Bank efficiency	1	2	3	4	5
1.	I can access the site quickly	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	It's easy to find what I need on the website	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	It's quick and easy to carry out a transaction via the bank's website.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	It doesn't take much effort to use the bank's website	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5.	The organisation and structure of online content is easy to follow	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section V: Profitability

Sno	Profitability	2018	2019	2020	2021
1.	Return on assets (ROA)				
2.	Return on equity (ROE)				
3.	Investments				
4.	Deposits				
5.	Total assets				

Section VI: Quality of banking services

The factors relating to the quality of banking services include the following statements using a 5-point rating scale ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree", with a score of 1 to 5 respectively.

(1) Strongly disagree, (2) d disagree, (3) n neutral, (4) a agree, (5) Strongly agree

Sno.	Quality of banking services	1	2	3	4	5
	Reliability axis					
1.	The Bank's actions strengthen customer security	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	The Bank keeps accurate records of transactions with customers	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	Providing an adequate explanation of the services provided to customers.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	Interested in solving customer problems.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5.	Undertakes to honour the promises made for the provision of a particular service	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	Response axis					
1.	Responding to customer requests despite professional pressures	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	The task is carried out according to the time needed to complete it	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	The service is offered to customers in several instalments with the same quality.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	Clear efforts are made to meet customer needs and align services appropriately.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5.	Don't worry about customers doing their own thing.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	Focus on the efficiency of service providers					
1.	Have the skills and knowledge required to carry out the service.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	Good communication skills and a good understanding of customers.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	Have the right training to do the job.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	Employees have the skills needed to provide high-quality services to customers.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

	Access axis					
1.	Easy access and communication.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	Shorten the waiting period for service.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	Provide a sufficient number of sockets to ensure service.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	Convenient working hours for customers	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	Focus on tact					
1.	Bank staff are distinguished and respected.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	The staff are friendly and kind to customers.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	Employees pay personal attention to their customers.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	Staff are well treated and courteous to guests.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	Axis of communication					
1.	Providing customers with information in a language they understand.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	Provide instructions on the nature and cost of the service.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	Provides information on alternatives to existing services.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	The Bank provides all information relating to the new services.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5.	Communication channels exist for the transfer of information between customers and management.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	Credibility axis					
1.	The services provided by the Bank are objective and meet quality objectives.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	The Bank monitors and controls the level of service provision.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	Services are performed with precision at the bank.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	Taking honesty and sincerity into account when dealing with customers.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	Safety hub					
1.	Undertake to maintain the confidentiality of customer accounts.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	Employee behaviour is marked by confidence and self-assurance.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	There are enough security guards at the bank.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	The Bank's operations are indisputable and serious.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	Sympathy axis					
1.	Every customer receives special attention.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	Put the customer's interests ahead of your own.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

3.	The bank's opening hours are convenient for all customers.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	The bank's employees treat all customer problems with interest.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5.	Customer service is one of their top priorities.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Emphasis on tangible physical and human aspects						
1.	Sufficient staff are available.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	The bank keeps abreast of the latest technological developments in banking.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	The latest equipment is available for the provision of services.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	The Bank has practical and attractive public facilities and amenities.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5.	The general appearance of the bank is consistent with the type of services provided.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section VII: Capital management

The capital management factors include the following statements on a 5-point rating scale ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree", with a score of 1 to 5 respectively.

(1) Strongly disagree, (2) d disagree, (3) n neutral, (4) a agree, (5) Strongly agree

Sno.	Capital management	1	2	3	4	5
1.	The lower the level of liquidity, the higher the risk of not being able to meet current obligations.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	There is a significant relationship between the performance variable and the working capital component.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	Effective working capital management affects short-term financial performance.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	Effective working capital management affects long-term financial performance.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5.	The reduction in the cash conversion cycle has a positive effect on the return on assets.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6.	Profitable companies follow a more formal policy.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7.	Managing receivables, inventories and payables has no impact on company profitability.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section VIII: Management efficiency

The management effectiveness factors include the following statements on a 5-point rating scale ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree", with a score of 1 to 5 respectively.

(1) Strongly disagree, (2) d disagree, (3) n neutral, (4) a agree, (5) Strongly agree

Sno.	Management efficiency	1	2	3	4	5
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1.	Well-capitalised banks are more stable and profitable	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	Our bank adopts budgets and planning as a tool for improving the efficiency of financial management.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	Our bank maintains optimum liquidity to meet depositors' cash requirements.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	Our bank's management is effective in making financial management decisions, which contributes to improved financial performance.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5.	Our bank is sufficiently capitalised, which means it is increasingly profitable	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6.	Our bank has complied with the central bank's capital adequacy requirements.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7.	Our bank has short-term receivables, which enables us to manage our liquidity more effectively.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8.	Our bank raises funds from the most profitable source and uses them in the most profitable investments to improve profitability.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section IX: Attitude to risk

Sno	Attitude to risk	1	2	3	4	5
1.	Risk management is an important element of management reporting (business plan for the coming year).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	The Bank is aware of the strengths and weaknesses of other banks' risk management systems.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	What areas of risk does the bank currently face the most? (Please rank each of these areas of risk to indicate the degree of risk they represent for your bank. Place 1 in the box corresponding to the riskiest area, 2 in the second riskiest area and so on. Do not put the same number in more than one box).					
	Credit risk		Liquidity risk		Operational risk	
	Market risk		Interest rate risk		Foreign exchange risk	
	Solvency risk		Model risk		Systematic risk	
	Other risks : Country, settlement, performance, etc.		Not applicable			
4.	What are the riskiest areas in your banking activities (Please rank each of these areas to indicate the degree of risk they represent for your bank. Place 1 in the box corresponding to the riskiest area, 2 in the second riskiest area and so on. Do not put the same number in more than one box).					
	Securities-linked loans		Property loans		Credit cards	
	Consumer loans		International regulations		Change	

	Other (please specify)	Not applicable	
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1. What is the Riksbank's inflation target?
1.0% 2.0% 3.0% Don't know

2. If there is a risk that the target will be exceeded, what should Riksbank do?
Reduce the repo rate Increase the repo rate Do nothing Not knowing

3. If the nominal interest rate is 5% and expected inflation is 2%, what will the real interest rate be (approximately)?
 2.5% 3.0% 7.0 % Don't know

4. A savings product in which you receive a guaranteed amount at maturity, and whose return tracks the equity market, is called a
 Equity funds Hedge fund Equity-linked security Don't know.

5. Mutual funds have different levels of risk. Which of these types of mutual fund is generally considered to have the highest risk?
 Balanced funds Bond funds Equity funds Don't know

Section X Financial results

The financial performance factors include the following statements on a 5-point rating scale ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree", with a score of 1 to 5 respectively.

(1) Strongly disagree, (2) d disagree, (3) n neutral, (4) a agree, (5) Strongly agree

Sno	Financial performance	1	2	3	4	5
1	Over the last three years, the bank's financial performance has outstripped that of its competitors.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2	The last three years have been more profitable for the bank than for our competitors.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3	Over the last three years, the bank's sales growth has outstripped that of its competitors.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4	The bank and its supply chain partners pool financial and non-financial resources.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5	Supply chain integration has significantly increased the return on assets.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6	The integration of the supply chain has significantly improved the rate of sales to key customers.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Thank you for your reply

Appendix 2

Figure 4.1.1 (a): Percentage for gender

